

THE INFLUENCE OF MUSIC ON HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY*M. Mirzayeva*¹*Abstract:*

This article is widely covered under the topic “The influence of music on human psychology”. It is explained that music not only affects human feelings, but also has the ability to heal a person. Also, in this article, it's mentioned about the history of the origin and the first concepts of music. In the Middle Ages, the influence of music on the human mind was explained by great thinkers. It is also emphasized that music can help with human stress and behavior. A person who reads this article will understand how important music plays in human life and psychology.

Key words: music, psychology, stress, behavior, history, scientists, antiquity

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Music is derived from the Greek word meaning "the art of the muses". It is an art from that reflects human emotions thoughts and imagination through musical sounds. Depending on the type of music, it has different effects on the mind and emotions of a person. Music plays an important role as a means of forming a person's moral and aesthetic taste, developing his emotional feelings. But also relieve physical pain. Therefore, we can also use it as medicine. Instead of further information, it can be said that when a person faces a death that frightens him, he expresses these feelings in various songs, for example, in mourning or funeral rites. and love and mourning songs were the first music created by man. Music is the traditional art and culture of all countries on earth. If we look at history, music came before even language. For example, before the emergence of language, humans spoke through sounds or used various objects as drums and other musical instruments. There are different types of music. For example, jazz, pop, rock and others. All people have different tastes in listening to music. Someone likes rock – loud songs, and someone likes quiet songs.

For a long time, scientist conducted experiments on the effect of music on human psychology. Many scholars have only theoretically discussed the functions of music. But because these experiments and discussions were not practical, various problems and contradictions arose among scientists. Some scientists have proven through experiments that music also has a supportive nature. For this way, people have come to understand the effect of music on mood, emotions and eve memory. The human brain adapts to sound and movement from 16 to 18 weeks in the womb. Especially the sense of hearing develops faster than other senses. From this we can understand that people tend to sound and hear it. This suggests that some parts of our brain function to be triggered by audio. Music has a powerful and often emotional effect on many people. But few people understand how music can physically affect the brain, it

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HUMANISTIC ROLE OF LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE IN THE CONTEMPORARY GLOBALIZATION

is important to understand how our body interacts with sounds. If we rely on experience, the famous Greek philosopher Plato said that the power of the state depends on what kind of music and rhythm is heard in it. On the other hand, the works of the authors of antiquity can also be the basis for this. For instance, the epic of the “Odyssey” describes the healing of a wound under the influence of music. To give another example, the Spartan ruler Lycurgus also composed music for his troops during battle. From this, we can know that, the psychology of music can hinder human mood and education. The Greek ruler also believed that music played a big role in winning the battle. Sometimes, many doctors consider the way of treatment through music to be correct. Music therapy is the most popular form of treatment. Scientist Ibn Sino also proved this in his research. Music has healing properties. It not only brings a person out of depression, but also relieves physical pain. Sometimes it comes out not only with many of the emotions. We experience every day and we encounter the event in life, also with the songs played on radio and TV. Music has such a power that once you hear a song, you can remember it for the rest of your life. And when you hear it again, you can predict how it will continue. We cannot get such impressive power from picture. For instance, if we see one picture, the next time we see it. It may look different. If we look at the influence of music on children’s upbringing, it affects every child differently.

However sometimes everyone has a question. Why does a child need music? On the one hand, this is strange question, but many parents say that we want our children to be spiritually rich. Children are very curious from a young age and have the ability to copy quickly. For this reason, many parents are careful when listening to music to their children. Because sometimes some music has strong tone and this music can have negative effects for children. But on the positive side it develops aesthetic taste in the child. And among his peers, he wins their attention and affection. In addition, music has a greater effect on the health and body of creative people, often they are either inspired by music or, on the contrary, bored by music. Music as a background is often imperceptible to us. It is really useful in shopping malls, restaurants, clothing stores, because it creates a unique atmosphere. Often, depending on the type of music, we can determine the reputation of the institution.

In conclusion, it can be said that human psychology and music are linked together. It has been scientifically proven that music has a direct effect on person’s mood and emotions then is capable of creating and changing them. Music’s shape effect on people experiences that not only we can conclusion form of art but also form of communication. As I mentioned below, song allow one to voice, thoughts and aspiration for better life. Scientist have long move that they fulfill positive effects for their mental health and quality of life. Playing music makes interact with world and boosting horizon.

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